

The Crystalline Constituents of Euphorbiaceae Part-IX : Triterpenes of *Euphorbia cattimandoo* W. Elliot.

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The commercial latex of *E. cattimandoo* contains euphol, nerifoliol and euphorbol while the stems contain taraxerol only.

Euphorbia cattimandoo, W. Elliot^{1,2} is synonymous with *E. Trigona*, Haw (Sanskrit: Vajrakantaka, Vajrakshiri and Samantadugdha; Hindi: Gridhara.). It is found extensively on the dry rocky hills of Visakhapatnam and Deccan. Its latex is drawn, mixed with flour and drawn into large thick wires which are sold after drying in the market under the trade name "cattimandoo". Indigenously, it is reported as a remedy for diseases of the respiratory tract, especially, cough, bronchitis and asthma. It is also reputed as a useful remedy in dysentery, colic and worms².

Henke³ observed that the latex of *Euphorbia cattimandoo* contained "euphorbone", a triterpenoidal mixture of *Euphorbia* latex of commerce. But no systematic identification of the components was reported so far.

In the present investigation, the alcoholic extract of the dried commercial latex was fractionated carefully. Euphol (I), nerifoliol (II) and euphorbol(III) were the chief components which separate out in fairly well defined fractions from the alcoholic extract when carefully concentrated. Purification of each fraction, however, requires different techniques. It was noticed that during chromatography on alumina euphol⁴ (I) generally comes

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., (India), 1956, p. 115.
2. R. N. Chopra, K. L. Handa and L. D. Kapur, "Indigenous Drugs of India", Dhur & Sons Ltd., Calcutta, 1958, p. 556.
3. G. Henke, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1886, **24**, 729.
4. D. Nageswara Rao and L. Ramachandra Row, *Curr. Sci.*, 1965, **34**, 432.

out in the petroleum ether eluate as an oil, from which it could be separated as acetate. Hydrolysis of the acetate usually furnished pure euphol (I). Benzene: pet. ether (1:1) removed nerifoliol⁴ (II) in fairly pure condition. It could be further purified by fractional crystallisation or through its benzoate.

When the final concentrates from several extractions were left for a pretty long time, workable quantities of euphorbol⁵ (III) separated out mixed with euphol (I). This mixture was separated by chromatography, pet. ether removed euphol completely and euphorbol (III) came in the benzene eluate.

Of these three triterpenes, nerifoliol (II) appears to be the largest in percentage (3%), euphol next (1.5%) and euphorbol (0.5%). Nerifoliol (II) usually crystallised from the crude extract along with the oily fraction. Separation of these two can be effected readily by chromatography on alumina as indicated above.

The stem constituents differed from those of the latex. The stems had the pentacyclic triterpene taraxerol⁶ (IV) (0.6%) as the sole crystalline constituent. It had been our experience that the latex triterpenes are usually tetracyclic triterpenes while the stem constituents were pentacyclic as in *E. antiquorum*, Linn^{5,6} and *E. nerifolia*, Linn^{4,7}.

The crystalline constituents so far isolated from *E. cattimandoo* did not lend any support to its medicinal reputation, nor do they suggest the vesicant nature of the fresh latex. Although some of these, particularly euphorbone, were official long ago, in the British and American pharmacopeas, they were discarded later. But the use of the dried or fresh latex by the local people still continues. A search for the minor constituents of the latex might be profitable in explaining the medicinal reputation.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Latex*. The dry commercial latex (500 g) of *E. cattimandoo* was extracted (2×11) by refluxing with alcohol. The extracts were separately collected and set aside. From the first extract, a colorless compound (12 g), Fraction A, m.p. 113-127° separated out after 12 hr. Another colourless compound (13 g), Fraction B, m.p. 113-122°, slowly separated out after two days. From the second extract, a colourless compound (12 g), Fraction C,

5. V. Anjaneyulu and L. Ramachandra Row, *Curr. Sci.*, 1967, **36**, 204.

6. V. Anjaneyulu, D. Nageswara Rao and L. Ramachandra Row, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 123.

7. V. Anjaneyulu and L. Ramachandra Row, *Curr. Sci.*, 1965, **34**, 608.

m.p. 122-28° slowly separated out after two weeks. The filtrates of the two extracts were mixed and concentrated (11) to give a colourless compound, Fraction D (12 g) m.p. 88-108°.

Fractions A and B were combined and crystallised from methanol, m.p. 115-130° (15 g). 5g of this solid was taken in benzene (15 ml) and chromatographed over alumina (150 g). Pet. ether eluted a gummy compound (4 g) and benzene eluted a colourless substance, m.p. 129-130° (compound B; 600 mg). The benzene eluate—did not yield any crystalline product. The pet. ether eluate was acetylated with pyridineacetic anhydride over a steam-bath for 3.5 hr. and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 106-107° (Compound A acetate).

Fraction C, after several crystallisations from methanol came out as colourless buttons, m.p. 129-130°. It was purified by chromatography over alumina. Pet. ether eluted an uncrystallisable oil and pet. ether: benzene (1:1) eluted compound B, recrystallised from methanol as colourless plates, m.p. 130-31°.

Fraction D, appeared to be a mixture and therefore, it was acetylated with Ac_2O -Py over a steam-bath for 3.5 hr. It could be fractionally separated from CHCl_3 -MeOH into two compounds, compound A acetate, m.p. 107-09° and compound C acetate, m.p. 123-125°. Compound A and C were also successfully separated by chromatography over alumina. Pet. ether eluted an oil. and after acetylation compound A acetate was isolated. Elution with benzene gave compound C.

Examination of Compound A acetate: Compound A acetate, crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 108-09°, (α)_D^{30°}+40° (C, 1.2 in CHCl_3), m.m.p. unchanged by authentic euphyl acetate. (Found: C, 82.08; H, 11.06; $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 82.66; H, 11.11%).

Hydrolysis of Compound A acetate: Euphol: Compound A acetate (500mg) in benzene (15 ml) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 8% alcoholic pot. hydroxide (50 ml) for 4 hr on a waterbath. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue poured into water. The solid was collected and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 117°, (α)_D^{30°}+35° (C, 1.8 in CHCl_3), unchanged by euphol. (Found: C, 84.41; H, 11.61; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.50; H, 11.74%).

Benzoate: (Pyridine+Benzoylchloride, steam-bath 3½ hr.). Crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH as colourless plates, m p. 138-140°, (C, 1.12 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 83.75; H, 10.40; $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 83.77; H, 10.19%).

Chromium trioxide oxidation of euphol: Euphone: Euphol (300 mg) in benzene (15 ml) was shaken with chromium trioxide (150 mg) in Analar acetic acid (10 ml) and water (10 ml) for 2½ hr at the room temperature. The excess of chromium trioxide was destroyed by adding a small quantity of methanol and the solution poured into water. It was extracted with ether and the extract washed with sodium carbonate solution, water and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . After removing ether, it was crystallised from methanol as short rods, m.p. 118-19°, (α)_D^{30°}+70° (C, 1.2 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 85.02; H, 11.25; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.89; H, 11.32%).

Examination of Compound B: Nerifoliol: Compound B, crystallised from methanol as colourless plates, m.p. 131-132°, (α)_D²⁰ +20° (C, 3.2 in CHCl₃), m.m.p. with authentic nerifoliol was undepressed. (Found: C, 84.5; H, 11.6; C₃₀H₅₀O requires C, 84.50; H, 11.74%).

Acetate: Nerifoliol (100 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (2 ml) treated with acetic anhydride (1 ml) and heated over a steam-bath for 3½ hr. It was crystallised from methanol as colourless needles m.p. 85-87° (α)_D³⁰ -37° (C, 0.9 in CHCl₃). (Found: C 82.0; H 10.8; C₃₂H₅₂O₂ requires C, 82.06; H, 11.11%).

Benzoate: (Pyridine-Benzoyl chloride, steam-bath 3½ hr.) Crystallised from methanol as colourless plates, m.p. 110-112°, (α)_D³⁰ -48° (C, 1.2 in CHCl₃). (Found: C, 83.6; H, 9.9; C₃₇H₅₄O₂ requires C, 83.77; H, 10.19%).

Chromium trioxide oxidation of Nerifoliol: Euphone: Nerifoliol (200 mg) in benzene (15 ml) was shaken with chromium trioxide (100 mg) in Analar acetic acid (10 ml) and water (10 ml) for 2½ hr at room temperature and worked up as in the case of euphol. It was crystallised from methanol as short rods, m.p. 118-119°, (α)_D³⁰ +19° (C, 1 in CHCl₃), unchanged by euphone.

Examination of Compound C acetate: Compound C acetate crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 124-25°, (α)_D³⁰ ±0° (C, 2.1 in CHCl₃). (Found: C, 82.08; H, 11.62; C₃₃H₅₄O₂ requires C, 82.17; H, 11.73%).

Hydrolysis of Compound C acetate: Euphorbol: Compound C acetate (300 mg) in benzene (15 ml) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 8% alcoholic pot. hydroxide (20 ml) for 4 hr on a water-bath and worked up in the usual way and crystallised from methanol as colourless plates, m.p. 126-127°, (α)_D³⁰ +0° (C, 1.8 in CHCl₃), unchanged by authentic euphorbol from *E. antiquorum*, Linn. (Found: C, 84.39; H, 11.45; C₃₁H₅₂O requires C, 84.53; H, 11.81%).

Benzoate: (Pyridine-Benzoyl chloride, Steam-bath 3½ hr.)—Crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as colourless needles, m.p. 134-135°, (α)_D³⁰ +22° (C, 1.3 in CHCl₃). (Found: C, 83.65; H, 11.67; C₃₈H₅₆O₃ requires C, 83.83; H, 10.29%).

Dibromide of Euphorbadienylacetate: Euphorbadienylacetate (200 mg) dissolved in ether (10 ml) was treated with bromine in glacial acetic acid (4%). The absorption of bromine was rapid and the addition continued until the colour of bromine was persistent. The solution was left over night and the ether removed under reduced pressure. The residue treated with water and the solid obtained crystallised from acetone-methanol as plates, m.p. 169-171°. (Found: C, 61.67; H, 8.63; C₃₃H₅₄O₂Br₂ requires C, 61.7; H, 8.414%).

(b). *Stems:* The sun-dried stems of the plant (240 g) were cut into small pieces and extracted continuously in a soxhlet apparatus with pet. ether, ether and alcohol.

The pet. ether extract (1.51) was concentrated to 100 ml. A colourless solid (m.p. 210-26° (1.60 g) separated out after several days. The filtrate upon further concentration gave a waxy solid (colourless crystals from benzene, m.p. 72-74°; 4.3 g). It was no more pursued. Ether and alcohol extracts were carefully examined, but no crystallisable solid could be secured.

The compound m.p. 210-26° was dissolved in pyridine (25 ml) treated with benzoyl chloride (5 ml) and heated over a steam-bath for 3hr. It was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH, as colourless prisms, m.p. 283-5°, (α)_D^{30°} +28.2° (C, 1 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 83.5; H, 10.4; $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 83.77; H, 10.19%). M.M.P. with taraxeryl benzoate undepressed.

Hydrolysis of taraxeryl benzoate: Taraxerol: Taraxeryl benzoate (400 mg) in benzene (20 ml) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 8% alcoholic pot. hydroxide (40 ml) for 3hr. on a steam-bath. It was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH as colourless needles, m.p. 282-83°, (α)_D^{30°} +0° (C, 1.1 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 84.4; H, 11.5; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.5; H, 11.74%) M.M.P. with authentic taraxerol undepressed.

Acetate: Colourless prisms from benzene, m.p. 294-6°, (α)_D^{30°} +10.8° (C, 1.2 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 82.2; H, 11.5; $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 82.06; H, 11.11%).

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